

*A Guidebook on Agricultural
Flood Adaptation for the
City of Ilagan*

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About this project

This guidebook is a product of an undergraduate thesis on agricultural flood adaptation in Ilagan City, Isabela. It serves as a guide for the Ilagan City community, particularly the local government and farmers, in implementing comprehensive flood adaptation measures for the region. It emphasizes the integration of indigenous and local knowledge with scientific measures to promote landscape-responsive approaches. By applying this guidebook, communities in Ilagan City can sustain the agricultural productivity of its land despite the perennial flooding concerns in the agricultural city.

May this book help Ilagan transform itself into a flood-adaptive agricultural city.

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How to use the guidebook?

What you will learn:

*Overview of the thesis project
Production of the guidebook
Contribution of the guidebook
Interpreting the guidebook*

Overview

Ilagan is a prime agricultural city in the country. Unfortunately, flooding is also part of the landscape of Ilagan due to its geographical location in Cagayan Valley. The geopolitical region constantly experiences considerable damage to its agricultural landscape and is threatened by a production decline due to flooding.

Hence, there is a need to devise adaptation measures to sustain the productivity of Ilagan's farmlands amidst its flooding concerns. An approach accentuating local knowledge is important to integrate at-risk communities' adaptation learnings with established risk science for a more effective agricultural flooding response.

In the next pages are scenarios and landscape-based solutions to answer the concerns of the agricultural city of Ilagan. These suggestions are achieved primarily through a focus group discussion with the Ibanag farming community to explore indigenous agricultural flood adaptation measures. Eventually, the solutions are supplemented with several interviews with agricultural experts and desk research to produce a toolkit of fifteen flood adaptation measures acknowledged by the scientific community. Overall, the flood-adaptive measures for Ilagan are anchored on cultural, environmental sensitivity, temporal, and physical measures.

With the integration of these knowledge types, tested through the community participatory workshop where local representatives shared their insights regarding agriculture in Ilagan and the proposed toolkit, three scenarios based on the pillar of climate-smart agriculture are created to achieve the most optimum condition per landscape type. Finally, a masterplan guided by the four core principles extracted from the Ibanag farmers and strengthened by the fifteen specific agricultural flood adaptation measures is presented as eight typologies to be considered for Ilagan City.

This guidebook, as part of a thesis project, hopes to become a basis for a flood-adaptive agricultural landscape plan informed by the integration of local and scientific knowledge for Ilagan City.

How was the guidebook produced?

Shown in the image is the research approach and work plan applied to produce the guidebook.

An inquiry into the current concerns in Ilagan leads to the framing of agricultural flood adaptation as the problem. Goals are established to identify the methods necessary to reach a possible resolution.

Initially, the site is classified into different agricultural classes by processing existing planning maps. A focus group discussion with the Ibanag farming community of Naguilian Norte is conducted to explore their agricultural flood adaptation. Moreover, insights from agricultural experts and published studies are used to supplement the data gathered from the Ibanag community. Lastly, a workshop with Ilagueno locals is conducted to understand their experiences, local knowledge, and preferences.

The collective knowledge formed from the previous methods is translated into three planning scenarios. Each is assessed based on the two pillars of climate-smart agriculture. From here, the chosen scenario is developed into a masterplan and translated into a guidebook. The guidebook ensures a more accessible dissemination of this study to the locals of Ilagan, especially the local government and farmers.

How will the guidebook help you?

Suggest agricultural practices and flood adaptation measures based on the Ibanag Community in Barangay Naguilan Norte

Identify best agricultural flood adaptation strategies and practices that can be adapted by Ilagan City

Assist the LGU and local farmers in implementing flood-adaptive strategies on city and on-farm scale respectively.

Target users

Local government unit of Ilagan

Local Ilagueno farmers

How to use the guidebook?

Here are your tasks:

R Recognize local conditions.

E Explore the proposed interventions.

F Fill out the review sheet to help you plan your flood-adaptive agricultural landscape.

What are the local conditions affecting Ilagan and my farm?

What you will learn:

*Types of agricultural lands based on flooding conditions
Environmental conditions relevant to agriculture and flooding
The collective knowledge of agricultural flood adaptation
State of the agricultural landscape in Ilagan*

Types of agricultural landscape in Ilagan based on their flood susceptibility

The agricultural lands are produced by combining the Strategic Agriculture and Fisheries Development Zone, landform, and flood susceptibility maps. Its purpose is to classify each farmland based on flooding events to better inform landscape solutions.

There are twenty-eight classes identified in the mapping procedure.

Reflect:

 What are the affected production areas needing prioritization?

 What class does your farm belong to?

The maps represent the existing spatial condition of Ilagan City. The land use and land cover maps reveal that the majority of the site is agricultural land. Moreover, these lands are divided administratively into four clusters. It can also be observed that the study area is relatively flat with the hilly and mountainous areas concentrated in the eastern portion.

Reflect:

How would the environmental conditions influence agricultural flooding in Ilagan?

What environmental conditions largely influence your farm?

The soil map indicates the type of soil available in Ilagan. Moreover, the Sthraler order reveals the riverway that caters the most water volume while the sub-basin map delineates the different catch basin areas in the city. Lastly, the agricultural support facilities map reveals the distribution of critical agricultural facilities in the city.

Collective knowledge as an adaptation strategy

The approach serves as the guiding principle for developing a flood-adaptive agricultural city. The core of the proposed solution lies in **cultural adaptation**--acceptance of flooding as an intrinsic part of the agricultural landscape. This core adaptation is complemented by:

environmental sensitivity: awareness of environmental changes

temporal: proper timing of agricultural activities; and

physical adaptation: tangible changes in the farmlands.

Together, they form the core guiding principles for agricultural flood adaptation. Lastly, the analyses of expert interviews and desk research produce fifteen specific agricultural flood adaptation measures which serve as supplementary strategies for the core guiding principles.

How would this affect the current flooding strategies of the city?

Reflect:

How is this different from your current farming practices?

agricultural flood adaptation approach for Ilagan

Status

This section gives a comprehensive overview of the current state of the agricultural landscape in Ilagan.

Drivers	Pressures	States	Impacts	Responses
<i>Agricultural Tradition</i>	Deforestation of the uplands	Degraded uplands, low biodiversity	Deposition in the waterways, landslide, flash flood, and flooding in the lowlands	Restoration of the upland areas by incorporating livelihood strategies with ecological functions.
<i>Primary Revenue</i>	Land conversion	Increase in non-agricultural areas	Flooding in the urban areas, smaller area of arable lands	Imposition of urban growth restriction and protection of prime agricultural areas.
<i>Fertile Land</i>	Flooding	23 barangays with flooded farms	Losses in finances, assets, and livelihood	Implementation of climate-resilient technologies and approaches with especial attention to flood adaptation.
<i>Food security</i>	Industrialization	Produce is still mostly limited to raw products	Lower product value	Venture into processing and marketing to add value in agricultural products.
	Monocropping farming system	Dominant corn and rice planting areas	Soil degradation and cycle of pest diseases	Implementation of sustainable farming systems that promote biodiversity and soil health.
	Excessive use of chemicals	Degraded soils	Environmental pollution, lower soil fertility	Adoption of organic or controlled use chemicals, and ecologically safe farming practices.
	Improper management of agricultural wastes	Degraded soils	Air and soil pollution, killing of microorganisms	Conversion of biomass into agricultural products or establishment agricultural waste management facilities.
	Rejection of sustainable farming knowledge and technology	Ill-equipped for flooding events	Low adaptive capacity	Information dissemination improvement and enactment of policies that will support and compel farmers toward sustainable farming methods and higher adaptive capacity.
	Government policies	High agricultural productivity	High self-sufficiency	Creation of policies and programs that will help Ilagueno farmers transition toward a productive and adaptive agricultural city.

Reflect: *What adjustments do you need to do to improve the condition of your agricultural landscape?*

What solutions apply to Ilagan's agricultural landscape?

What you will learn:

Proposed flood-adaptive zones

Proposed masterplan

On-farm strategies

Knowing the different flood-adaptive zones

Riparian Restoration Zone

It is an intensive production area characterized by its integrated flood adaptation measures. Integrated farming system best describes the zone.

Multi-functional Agricultural Zone

This serves as a minimal agriculture zone characterized by wet farming and strict agricultural practices.

Core guiding principles and specific agricultural flood adaptation measures applied:

● cultural ● environmental sensitivity ● temporal ● physical

Knowing the different flood-adaptive zones

Flood Resilient Agricultural Zone

An intensive production agriculture area characterized by its integrated flood adaptation measures

Agroforestry Zone

Agriculture in this zone is characterized by improved water storage and intense production to contribute to the city's overall flood adaptation and agricultural production.

Core guiding principles and specific agricultural flood adaptation measures applied:

● cultural ● environmental sensitivity ● temporal ● physical

Knowing the different flood-adaptive zones

Forest Zone

A zone that contributes to flood adaptation through watershed restoration and water storage facilities.

Agro-Industrial Zone

The zone caters to the needs of the city for efficient production while increasing the extent of the socially constructed desirable regime by diversifying the livelihoods and augmenting the income of farmers.

Core guiding principles and specific agricultural flood adaptation measures applied:

● cultural ● environmental sensitivity ● temporal ● physical

Knowing the different flood-adaptive zones

Multi-functional Fisheries Zone

It focuses on establishing several fish farms in the city to support the intention of the LGU to continuously improve their production while acting as a reservoir for runoff water from the uplands.

Agro-resilience Technology Zone

A highly intensive production area guided by smart technologies to increase productivity. It is also equipped with flood adaptation measures to increase the floodable area in the city.

Core guiding principles and specific agricultural flood adaptation measures applied:

● cultural ● environmental sensitivity ● temporal ● physical

Putting the zones together

Three scenarios are proposed to support flood adaptation in the agricultural landscape of Ilagan. The differences in each scenario are evident in the number of utilized flood-adaptive zones. These are formulated focusing on the coexistence of agriculture and flooding as a form of adaptation. The goal is to assess the most optimum solution for the identified concern. Each zone was given a score based on their performance on food security and adaptation. The three zones are: comprehensive adaptation, targeted intervention, and baseline scenario.

Choosing the best scenario

assessment

12

food security pillar

3-highest; 1-lowest

<i>Food production</i>	3
<i>Animal production</i>	3
<i>Income</i>	3
<i>Consumption</i>	3

27

adaptation pillar

<i>Skills and knowledge</i>	3
<i>Access to information</i>	3
<i>Crop adaptation</i>	2
<i>Crop diversity</i>	3
<i>Animal diversity</i>	3
<i>Soil protection</i>	3
<i>Farm productivity</i>	3
<i>Stability of farm productivity</i>	2
<i>Income stability</i>	3
<i>Animal adaptation</i>	2

total score **39**

The scenario considers agricultural flood adaptation measures throughout the site. Interventions are even utilized in non-agricultural areas. It adheres to the recommendation of the experts to take a holistic approach--a ridge-to-reef one for flood adaptation. This is the chosen scenario for development into a masterplan.

Choosing the best scenario

assessment

food security pillar

3-highest; 1-lowest

Food production	2
Animal production	1
Income	3
Consumption	2

adaptation pillar

Skills and knowledge	3
Access to information	2
Crop adaptation	2
Crop diversity	2
Animal diversity	2
Soil protection	2
Farm productivity	2
Stability of farm productivity	2
Income stability	2
Animal adaptation	2

total score **29**

SCENARIO 2: TARGETED INTERVENTION SCENARIO

The scenario presents a reduction of strategies utilized in the first scenario because it only implements agricultural flood adaptation measures for flood-affected farms. This is a response towards efficient allocation of resources by targeting only areas that need interventions.

Choosing the best scenario

assessment

food security pillar

3-highest; 1-lowest

Food production	2
Animal production	2
Income	1
Consumption	2

adaptation pillar

Skills and knowledge	1
Access to information	1
Crop adaptation	1
Crop diversity	1
Animal diversity	1
Soil protection	1
Farm productivity	2
Stability of farm productivity	1
Income stability	1
Animal adaptation	1

total score

18

SCENARIO 3: BASELINE SCENARIO

This scenario presents a do-nothing approach. The assumption is that the agricultural landscape of Ilagan proceeds with their business-as-usual practices.

How to Read the Plan?

The plan consists of two main layers: the zoning and the planning diagrams. The zoning diagram is represented by the shapeless forms in solid color while the planning diagram is represented as point and linear elements in the map.

The planning diagram consists of five layers. In the plan, all are mapped except for the agricultural calendar to avoid visual confusion as it overlaps with all zones. It must be noted that only the multifunctional agriculture and flood-resilient agriculture zones adopt a shift in the agricultural calendar given their exposure to high and moderate flooding respectively.

How to use the information provided?

For the LGU

- 1. Look at the masterplan. Check the general location of the zones.*
- 2. Go to the proposal diagrams. Take note of the different interventions under the planning diagram. Also, check the general location of each zone.*
- 3. Review the framework plan. Look for the ideal proposed interventions to support each zone's function.*
- 4. Proceed to the on-farm strategies. Check out the sample design for each zone. These indicate model sites in the masterplan.*

For the farmers

- 1. Look at the masterplan. Check the location of your farmland and its designated flood-adaptive zone.*
- 2. Go to the framework plan and look up your assigned zone. Focus on the “proposed intervention” section and take note of the general flood-adaptive measures recommended for your farm.*
- 3. Proceed to the on-farm strategies and look for a sample design under your zone. Consider these when designing your farm as a flood-adaptive production area. Note that there are numerous ways to translate the proposed interventions into specific on-farm strategies.*

masterplan

Legend

- | | | |
|---|------------------------------------|----------------------------------|
| Site Boundary | Riparian Restoration Zone | Flood Resilient Agriculture Zone |
| Small Reservoir and Irrigation Projects | Agro-Resilience Technology Zone | Agro-industrial Zone |
| Integrated Agricultural Hub | Multi-functional Fisheries Zone | Riverbed |
| Riverbank Renaturation | Forest Zone | Built-up Areas |
| Road Network | Agroforestry Zone | |
| Waterways | Multi-functional Agricultural Zone | |

Proposal diagrams

The planning diagram covers landscape interventions that tie up the whole plan while the zoning diagram reflects the eight typologies of agricultural flood adaptation. Together, they constitute the comprehensive adaptation approach for the agricity of Ilagan.

PLANNING PROPOSAL DIAGRAM

ZONING DIAGRAM

Framework Plan

For the LGU: this serves as a guide on how to implement the proposed strategies on a city/zone scale. It details the core adaptation measures the city must implement for each zone alongside the specific recommended measures.

For the farmers: this informs them of the changes in their farm classification as seen in the masterplan. More importantly, the framework plan assists them in considering and implementing on-farm strategies appropriate to their farmlands (See Proposed Intervention). After the general considerations, landscape interventions become their next consideration. The next section details out more specific solutions.

What solutions apply to my farm?

On-farm landscape interventions

This section presents a possible translation of the proposed intervention presented in the framework plan. The purpose of the blow-up plans is to give farmers ideas on what to implement in their farms after considering the proposed interventions recommended for their zone location. Note that the landscape areas included in the plans are only some of the possible translations of the proposed interventions. Moreover, the plans are designed as model sites so there are landscape functions that are not necessarily replicable to farms that are not intended to be showcase areas. Ultimately, these are just the minimum considerations the farmers must adopt for their farms to conform to the function of their designated zones. The plans are not templates to be replicated but are guides on what to include as they transition into flood-adaptive agricultural landscapes.

Agroforestry Zone

- a- drop off area*
- b- parking area*
- c- bus parking area*
- d- educational building*
- e- observation area*
- f- agroforest*
- g- demonstration area*
- h- nursery area*
- i- hedgerow*

Agroforestry Zone

The agroforestry zone is an intensive production area. It encompasses the existing agroforests in the city and the converted hilly agricultural areas. In terms of flood adaptation, the zone contributes by arresting soil erosion and improving the water storage capacity of the uplands. Note that the blow-up plan is a model site. It is expected that functions catering to the influx of visitors, will not be considered in the development of farms not intended as showcase areas. Instead, they must consider functions focusing on production, soil erosion measures, and water storage.

Drop-off area: Provides visitors with a welcoming environment as they enter the model farm

Parking area: Accommodates visitors with cars and provides space for service vehicle

Bus parking area: Accommodates educational tours or field trips

Educational building: An area dedicated to learning and seminars.

Observation area: It serves as the tourism area in the plan. It enables visitors to immerse themselves in the landscape and have an overview of the different functions of the agroforest.

Demonstration area: Provides visitors with the chance to have a hands-on learning experience.

Agroforests: Rows of trees and crops used for soil protection and agricultural production. Moreover, these are the main elements utilized in improving the water storage capacity of the uplands.

Nursery area: Dedicated area for propagating tree and crop seedlings

Hedgerows: Main feature used in arresting soil erosion in the upland.

Agro-industrial Zone

- a*-service road
- b*-post-harvest facility
- c*-marketing facility
- d*-car parking area
- e*-truck parking area
- f*-post-processing facility
- g*-educational building
- h*-public space
- i*-livestock area
- j*-elevated walkway
- k*-water harvesting facility
- l*-vegetation buffer

Agro-industrial Zone

The agro-industrial zone is an intensive production area catering to mass and efficient production. In terms of flood adaptation, the zone contributes by expanding the desirable regime through livelihood diversification. It also houses a water harvesting facility and a large expanse of vegetated areas to ensure better infiltration of runoff. All agro-industrial sites are mandated to include water harvesting facilities and large vegetated areas as physical flood adaptation measures even though the zone itself is not susceptible to flood hazards. The reason is to red the accumulation of runoff in designated production areas.

Service road: Caters to incoming trucks and farmers intending to use the facilities.

Car parking area: Provides space for the vehicles of the farmers and visitors.

Truck parking area: Provides space for the trucks used for transporting goods produced in the facilities.

Post-harvest facility: Caters to the needs of farmers for efficient post-harvest service, especially during rainy seasons.

Marketing facility: A space provided for farmers where they can sell their products

Livestock area: It houses mass production of staple livestock and their products to promote food security in the city.

Post-processing facility- A facility dedicated to transforming agricultural wastes into agricultural products.

Educational building: Provides spaces for visitors who want to learn best practices in production.

Public space: The zone dedicates public spaces at its peripheries for the use of visitors and nearby communities.

Elevated walkway: A recreational feature for the visitors and nearby locals

Water harvesting facility: Stores runoff water to avoid accumulation in other areas, especially in farmlands

Vegetation buffer: Contributes to the attenuation of runoff discharge rate.

Agroresilient Technology Zone

- a-drop-off area
- b-parking area
- c-educational facility
- d-bus parking facility
- e-farm plot
- f-nursery area
- g-materials recovery facility
- h-high-value crops
- i-livestock area
- j-demonstration area
- k-smart-sensor tower
- l-water harvesting area
- m-observation deck
- n-service road
- o-vegetated buffer

Agro-resilient Technology Zone

The agro-resilient technology zone is a highly intensive production area in the plan. Given the absence of flood hazards, it can focus on increasing yield per cropping and even increase the cropping seasons to three using advanced technologies and short-maturing crop varieties. The zone promotes the use of smart farming practices to ensure efficient resource utilization and boost production. The increased production is also expected to offset the loss in agricultural areas converted into riparian restoration functions. In terms of agricultural flood adaptation, the zone contributes by dedicating spaces for water storage and regulated redirection of flood waters. In other terms, it increases the floodable area in the city.

Drop-off area: Provides visitors with a welcoming environment as they enter the model farm

Parking area: Accommodates visitors with cars and provides space for service vehicle

Bus parking area: Accommodates educational tours or field trips

Educational building: An area dedicated to learning, seminars, and research facilities.

Farm plots: Areas dedicated to intense production of rice and/or corn.

Nursery area: Dedicated area for propagating tree and crop seedlings

Materials recovery facility: A facility dedicated to handling agricultural wastes to address possible blocking of drainage ways.

High-value crops: A production area dedicated to cultivating high-value crops used to augment the income of farmers.

Livestock area: An area dedicated to raising various farm animals to augment the income of farmers.

Demonstration area: Provides visitors with the chance to have a learning experience.

Smart-sensor tower: It provides accurate data for weather forecasts, crop monitoring, and other resource utilization data to help farmers better plan their agricultural activities.

Water harvesting area: A small-farm reservoir for runoff to reduce accumulation in flood-affected farms and for later use during the dry season.

Observation deck: A recreational landscape feature catering to the visitors.

Service road: A dedicated path for farm vehicles.

Vegetated buffer: A green infrastructure used to improve water infiltration and attenuation.

Vegetated drainage canals: The area dedicated to accommodating redirected and regulated flood waters from the flood-affected farms.

Flood-resilient Agriculture Zone

- a-car parking area
- b-drop-off area
- c-marketing center
- d-educational building
- e-bus parking area
- f-tree grove
- g-nursery area
- h-high value crops
- i-farm plots
- j-livestock area
- k-utility area
- l-materials recovery facility

- m-water harvesting facility
- n-vegetated buffer
- o-vegetated drainage canal

flood level (1.5 m)

Flood-resilient Technology Zone

The zone is dedicated to intense production while considering the need for proactive flood adaptation measures. Structures must be limited to a minimum to avoid greater asset loss in the event of flooding. Moreover, the zone must strictly adhere to the recommended flood-adaptive cropping calendar and practices to avoid considerable crop damage. Practices in the zone include the adoption of soil conservation measures, water harvesting, change of livestock types, change in crop variety, and diversification of livelihood. All these aim to improve the desirable condition of the farming communities in the zone in the event of flooding.

Drop-off area: Provides visitors with a welcoming environment as they enter the model farm

Parking area: Accommodates visitors with cars and provides space for service vehicle

Bus parking area: Accommodates educational tours or field trips

Educational building: An area dedicated to learning and seminars.

Marketing area: Space for selling fresh or processed products.

Tree grove: Rows of trees providing alternative yield to farmers in case of flooding events.

Farm plots: Areas dedicated to intense production of rice and/or corn.

Nursery area: Dedicated area for propagating tree and crop seedlings

Materials recovery facility: A facility dedicated to handling agricultural wastes to address possible blocking of drainage ways.

High-value crops: A production area dedicated to cultivating high-value crops used to augment the income of farmers.

Livestock area: An area dedicated to raising flood-adaptive farm animals to augment the income of farmers.

Utility area: Stock room for several farm equipment and machinery.

Water harvesting area: A small-farm reservoir for runoff to reduce accumulation in flood-affected farms and for later use during the dry season.

Vegetated buffer: A green infrastructure used to improve water infiltration and attenuation.

Vegetated drainage canals: The area dedicated to improving the drainage flow in the zone. It also contributes to the faster draining of floodwaters after a flooding event.

Forest Zone

- a-drop-off area
- b-parking area
- c-tourist center
- d-office building
- e-reforested area
- f-eco-trail
- g-water harvesting facility
- h-observation deck
- i-control room
- j-observation tower

Forest Zone

The zone is a dedicated area for ecological restoration given its critical location near the Northern Sierra Madre Natural Park. The purpose of the zone is to address runoff concerns in the upland by improving its water storage capacity and restoring the watershed.

Drop-off area: Provides visitors with a welcoming environment as they enter the model farm

Parking area: Accommodates visitors with cars and provides space for service vehicle

Bus parking area: Accommodates educational tours or field trips

Educational building: An area dedicated to learning and seminars.

Marketing area: Space for selling fresh or processed products.

Tree grove: Rows of trees providing alternative yield to farmers in case of flooding events.

Farm plots: Areas dedicated to intense production of rice and/or corn.

Nursery area: Dedicated area for propagating tree and crop seedlings

Materials recovery facility: A facility dedicated to handling agricultural wastes to address possible blocking of drainage ways.

High-value crops: A production area dedicated to cultivating high-value crops used to augment the income of farmers.

Livestock area: An area dedicated to raising flood-adaptive farm animals to augment the income of farmers.

Utility area: Stock room for several farm equipment and machinery.

Water harvesting area: A small-farm reservoir for runoff to reduce accumulation in flood-affected farms and for later use during the dry season.

Vegetated buffer: A green infrastructure used to improve water infiltration and attenuation.

Vegetated drainage canals: The area dedicated to improving the drainage flow in the zone. It also contributes to the faster draining of floodwaters after a flooding event.

Multifunctional Agriculture Zone

- a-drop-off area
- b-educational building
- c-car parking area
- d-bus parking area
- e-tree grove plantation
- f-wet farm
- g-rice field
- h-water-harvesting facility
- i-livestock area
- j-utility zone
- k-vegetated buffer

flood level (2.0 m)

Multifunctional Agriculture Zone

Agriculture in the zone is strictly regulated to ensure proper practices are followed. This includes the adoption of flood-adaptive calendars, wet agriculture, water harvesting, and tree farming. These crucial measures contribute to the expansion of desirable conditions by diversifying the livelihood of farmers and ensuring properly timed agricultural activities.

Drop-off area: Provides visitors with a welcoming environment as they enter the model farm

Parking area: Accommodates visitors with cars and provides space for service vehicle

Bus parking area: Accommodates educational tours or field trips

Educational building: An area dedicated to learning and seminars.

Tree grove: A collection of perennial trees to offer farmers alternative produce in case of a flooding event.

Wet farm: Dedicated spaces for Trojan farming system. Crop selection must not be sensitive to flooding conditions.

Rice farm: Dedicated space for rice planting only.

Livestock area: An area dedicated to raising flood-adaptive farm animals to augment the income of farmers.

Utility area: It includes the materials recovery facility, stock room, and nursery facilities.

Water harvesting area: A small-farm reservoir for runoff to reduce accumulation in flood-affected farms and for later use during the dry season. It can also be utilized as a fish pond.

Vegetated buffer: A green infrastructure used to improve water infiltration and attenuation.

Multifunctional Fisheries Zone

- a-drop-off area
- b-parking area
- c-marketing area
- d-processing area
- e-educational facilities
- f-tourist area
- g-fish farm
- h-observation area
- i-bridge
- j-fish hatcheries
- k-materials recovery facility
- l-water harvesting facility
- m-vegetated buffer

Multifunctional Fisheries Zone

It is a dedicated production area for fish and its related products. The purpose is to improve the annual production of fish products and contribute to food security in the city. Its location at the foothills of the upland areas makes it ideal for water collection and supplementary soil erosion measures. Moreover, it contributes to livelihood diversification by offering flood-affected farmers alternative jobs in fish production during flooding season.

Drop-off area: Provides visitors with a welcoming environment as they enter the model farm

Parking area: Accommodates visitors with cars and provides space for service vehicle

Bus parking area: Accommodates educational tours or field trips

Educational building: An area dedicated to learning and seminars.

Processing area: Area for processing fish into value-added products.

Marketing area: Space for selling fresh or processed products.

Fish farm: Dedicated pond for raising a variety of fish types.

Observation area: An area dedicated to on-site and hands-on learning experiences.

Nursery area: Dedicated area for propagating tree and crop seedlings

Bridge: A unique element to the site selected. It is used to bridge the hatchery to the fish farms.

Livestock area: An area dedicated to raising flood-adaptive farm animals to augment the income of farmers.

Materials recovery facility: A space where farm wastes are managed to avoid contaminating the ponds.

Water harvesting area: A small farm reservoir to catch runoff water from the uplands. The captured water can also be used for irrigating the vegetated areas.

Vegetated buffer: A green infrastructure used to arrest soil erosion, improve water infiltration, and attenuate flow discharge rate.

Riparian Restoration Zone

- a-gathering area
- b-eco-trail
- c-community space
- d-mounded area
- e-constructed wetland
- f-elevated walkway
- g-vegetated area
- h-running trail
- i-vegetation buffer
- j-aquaculture area
- k-observation deck

flood level (2.0 m)

Riparian Restoration Zone

The zone is a strictly no-farm area. Only aquaculture activities are encouraged given its adjacency to the river. The zone serves as the main line of defense against floodwater, Unlike traditional flood prevention measures, the zone houses water storing and attenuating features. It emphasizes the accommodation of flood over prevention. It is mainly characterized by improved ecological areas, constructed wetlands, and a community space for the site selected. However, the majority of the zone outside the designed site will focus only on ecological habitat functions, water storage, and flow discharge rate attenuation.

Gathering area: It serves as a meeting place for the locals visiting the area.

Eco-trail: It provides a guided tour of the place covering all the important features.

Community space: It is a unique design element for the selected site given its adjacency to existing settlement areas. More importantly, it serves as a temporary observation area for researchers monitoring the zone's ecological health.

Mounded area: An aesthetic addition to improve recreational activities. It can serve as a picnic area for visitors.

Constructed wetland: The dominant feature of the site that caters to water storage functions. Its purpose is to lessen the volume of water reaching the adjacent production areas.

Elevated walkway: A recreational facility where visitors can closely experience the wetland and the river.

Vegetated areas: A supplementary feature promoting the improvement of water infiltration and flow discharge rate attenuation. More importantly, it provides critical habitats for the wildlife in the area.

Running trail: Another recreational element that can be utilized by the nearby community for health reasons or contemplation.

Vegetation buffer: A staple feature of the site alongside the wetland and vegetated areas. It serves as the main defense line against raging flood waters. Hence, plant selection must be water-tolerant and of good density.

Aquaculture area: A space dedicated to the fisherfolks. It includes fish farms to help them have stable production.

Observation deck: Another recreational element that promotes the re-establishment of people's connection with the river.

Policy Interventions

These are legal adjustments the LGU needs to implement to support the effective implementation of the masterplan.

Legal and Regulatory Framework

1. Comply with laws for agricultural resilience to floods and climate change, such as RA 9729 and RA 10121, by integrating flood-adaptive planning into local climate adaptation strategies and establishing a team for managing flooded agricultural resources.
2. Enhance the agricultural sector in line with RA 8435 to ensure equitable and profitable development, focusing on food security, industrialization, consolidation, productivity, and market efficiency.
3. Enforce RA 9003 for proper management of agricultural wastes to address behavioral challenges raised by stakeholders.
4. Prioritize environmental restoration in upland areas and prohibit agriculture in reforested areas as mandated by laws such as RA 2706 and PD 705 to maintain forest cover and prevent conversion of reforested lands into agricultural use.

Financial Support

1. Allocate annual budget in compliance with RA 9279 and RA 10174, known as the People's Survival Fund Act of 2012, to finance climate change projects in the city. This funding will support agricultural adaptation to climate change, supplemented by related agencies and donors, providing financial support to affected farmers, including subsidies for those lacking financial capacity.
2. Provide tax incentives to proactive landowners engaged in agricultural flood adaptation as a means of incentivizing their efforts.
3. Ensure that all farmers are covered by the Philippine Crop Insurance Corporation or similar insurance providers to mitigate risks associated with agricultural activities.

Policy Interventions

Upskilling and Capacity Building

1. Conduct regular seminars to disseminate information, focusing on best practices in agricultural flood adaptation and technologies.
2. Partner with the Department of Agriculture to build Adaptation and Mitigation Initiatives in Agriculture (AMIA) Villages, providing learning opportunities for farmers.
3. Organize regular hands-on training sessions for farmers to keep them updated on the latest developments, facilitating the dissemination of research innovations and gathering relevant field data directly from farmers.
4. Establish research centers in collaboration with state universities to facilitate the dissemination of findings and developments to local farmers.

Local Engagement

1. Establish satellite agriculture offices across the city to ensure farmers have easy access to services and can provide feedback on government projects.
2. Conduct an annual meeting with farmers to address their issues and preferences, aiding the LGU in short and long-term planning for the agriculture sector.
3. Facilitate farmers' consolidation to enhance the representation of the agricultural industry in all relevant matters, particularly in planning initiatives.
4. Engage indigenous communities as promoted by RA 8371, the Indigenous Peoples' Rights Act of 1997, to develop specific agricultural interventions tailored to their context, especially in upland areas.

Policy Interventions

Regional Collaboration

1. The Department of Agriculture Regional Field Office 2 will lead a multi-stakeholder and multi-scalar approach for agricultural flood adaptation in the entire region. Collaboration among different government agencies will ensure the regional implementation of the masterplan. The agricultural flood adaptation plan in Ilagan will serve as a model and pilot site for extending this approach to the entire valley region, especially in upstream and upland areas.
2. Consistently involve the private and non-government sectors in the planning and implementation of strategies.
3. Foster synergies between programs implemented by different agencies, particularly in environmental resource management, agriculture, disaster management, and budgeting departments.
4. Integrate existing climate change and environmental programs, such as the Alcala Green Wall and Amulung's greening projects along the banks of the Cagayan River, into the scaling of the masterplan.

Landscape Interventions

Constructed Wetland

The constructed wetland is a vital component of the riparian restoration zone. Its location within the very high flood susceptible zones makes it an important water storage feature contributing to the increase of floodable areas in the city. The wetland serves as a flood defense that accommodates flood instead of resisting it. Moreover, it also serves as an important ecological habitat restoring degraded areas caused by agricultural conversion

LEGEND

- 1 COMPACTED SUB-GRADE
- 2 150 MM THK GRAVEL BASE COURSE
- 3 50 MM THK SANDBED
- 4 VERTIGROW 2 MM THK NON-WOVEN GEOTEXTILE
- 5 3 MM THK VERTIGROW GEOSYNTHETIC CLAY LINER (GCL)
- 6 400 MM THK SOIL MIX
- 7 RANDOMLY PLACED MEDIUM-SIZED BOULDERS

Landscape Interventions

On-farm Small-water Harvesting Facility

On-farm small-water harvesting ponds serve as a water storage feature for farms affected by flooding. Runoff water that may affect plants during the rainy season is directed here using a network of on-farm earth canals. Moreover, the pond will also act as an irrigation facility, especially for farmers who may be affected by drought due to a shift in the agricultural calendar.

LEGEND

- 1 COMPACTED SUB-GRADE
- 2 150 MM THK GRAVEL BASE COURSE
- 3 50 MM THK SANDBED
- 4 VERTIGROW 2 MM THK NON-WOVEN GEOTEXTILE
- 5 3 MM THK HIGH DENSITY POLYETHYLENE (HDPE) LINER

Landscape Interventions

Bioswales

These bioswales are designed for the non-agricultural areas to improve water infiltration. These are recommended to be utilized in parking areas, streetscapes, and large expanse of vegetated areas. Alongside revegetation, bioswales act as a complementary strategy of upland restoration by improving water storage in the lowland area. The same detail can also be applied to the proposed vegetated drainage canals found at the peripheries of individual farm plots. These canals are used to convey runoff water toward the main catchment area and attenuate flow discharge rate.

LEGEND

- 1 COMPACTED SUB-GRADE
- 2 150 MM THK GRAVEL BASE COURSE
- 3 500 MM THK FILTERING SAND
- 4 500 MM THK GRAVEL BASE COURSE
- 5 400 MM THK SOIL MIX
- 6 150 MM THK GRAVEL BED
- 7 4" Ø PERFORATED DRAIN PIPE WRAPPED IN FILTER FABRIC

General Planting Concept

riparian restoration zone

The riparian restoration zone prioritizes the establishment of ecological area within lowland Ilagan. The selection utilizes native tree species to facilitate habitat restoration. The shrubs are based on their capacity to tolerate wet conditions.

trees

Terminalia macrocarpa
Kalumpit

Pterocarpus indicus
Narra

Terminalia calamansanai
Malakalumpit

Canarium luzonicum
Piling-liitan

Dracontomelon edule
Lamio

shrubs

Colocasia esculenta
Taro

Pteris vittate
Brake fern

Typha angustifolia
Narrow-leaved cattail

Canna indica
Canna lily

Iris pseudocorus
Yellow iris

General Planting Concept

Multifunctional Agricultural Zone

The species of plants used in the zone focuses on flood-tolerant crops, high-value crops, buffer strip plants, and windbreakers.

trees

Calophyllum inophyllum
Bitaoag

Diospyros blancoi
Kamagong

Vitex parviflora
Molave

Milletia pinnata
Bani

Lagerstroemia speciosa
Banaba

shrubs

Ixora chinensis
Santan

Tabernaemontana pandacaqui
Pandakaki

Carmona retusa
Tsaang-gubat

Strelitzia reginae
Bird of paradise

Podocarpus macrophyllus
Maki

crops

Oryza sativa
Rice: PSB Rc18 (Ala), NSIC Rc194 (Submarino 1), PSB Rc68 (Sacobia)

Manihot esculenta
Cassava

Citrullus lanatus
Watermelon

General Planting Concept

Flood-resilient Agricultural Zone

The plant species in this zone are dominated by industrial crops namely corn and rice. However, trees and shrubs are also present for windbreaking purposes and flood discharge rate attenuation

trees

Dipterocarpus grandifloras
Apitong

Anisoptera thurifera
Palosapis

Terminalia macrocarpa
Kalumpit

Pterocarpus indicus
Narra

shrubs

Ixora chinensis
Santan

Tabernaemontana pandacaqui
Pandakaki

Carmona retusa
Tsaang-gubat

Strelitzia reginae
Bird of paradise

Podocarpus macrophyllus
Maki

crops

Oryza sativa
Rice: PSB Rc18 (Ala), NSIC Rc194 (Submarino 1), PSB Rc68 (Sacobia)

Manihot esculenta
Cassava

Citrullus lanatus
Watermelon

Vigna radiata
Mungbean

Cucurbita maxima
Kalabasa

General Planting Concept

Agroforestry Zone

The plant selection in the zone is dictated by agricultural production. This means that the selected plant species contribute to augmenting farmers' income.

trees

Mangifera indica
Mango

Annona muricata
Guyabano

Citrus maxima
Pomelo

Sandoricum koetjape
Santol

Pterocarpus indicus
Narra

shrubs

Ixora chinensis
Santan

Tabernaemontana pandacaqui
Pandakaki

Carmona retusa
Tsaang-gubat

Strelitzia reginae
Bird of paradise

Podocarpus macrophyllus
Maki

crops

Ipomoea batatas
Sweet potato

Momordica charantia
Ampalaya

Solanum melongana
Eggplant

Solanum lycopersicum
Tomato

Cucurbita maxima
Kalabasa

General Planting Concept

Forestry Zone

The species used in the zone are mainly trees that are endemic or indigenous to Isabela. The general planting concept focuses on reforestation and ecological restoration.

trees

Hopea acuminata
Kasiray

Leucaena leucocephala
Ipil

Shorea contorta
White lauan

Vitex parviflora
Molave

Pterocarpus indicus
Narra

shrubs

Ixora chinensis
Santan

Tabernaemontana pandacaqui
Pandakaki

Carmona retusa
Tsaang-gubat

Strelitzia reginae
Bird of paradise

Podocarpus macrophyllus
Maki

General Planting Concept

Agro-industrial Zone

The general planting concept for the zone revolves on urban reforestation, phytoremediation, and recreational function.

trees

Cynometra ramiflora
Balitbitan

Alstonia scholaris
Dita

Clerodendrum quadriloculare
Bagawak-morado

Peltophorum pterocarpum
Siar

Vitex parviflora
Molave

shrubs

Ixora chinensis
Santan

Tabernaemontana pandacaqui
Pandakaki

Carmona retusa
Tsaang-gubat

Strelitzia reginae
Bird of paradise

Podocarpus macrophyllus
Maki

phytoremediating plants

Colocasia esculenta
Taro

Pteris vittata
Brake fern

Typha angustifolia
Narrow-leaved cattail

Canna indica
Canna lily

Iris pseudocorus
Yellow iris

General Planting Concept

Multi-functional Fisheries Zone

The selection of plant species for the zone is dictated by the wet nature of the area. Hence, species that can thrive along waterways or tolerate wet condition are prioritized in the palette

trees

Terminalia macrocarpa
Kalumpit

Dracontomelon edule
Lamio

Ficus variegata
Tangisang-bayawak

Polyscias nodosa
Malapapaya

Pterocarpus indicus
Narra

shrubs

Ixora chinensis
Santan

Tabernaemontana pandacaqui
Pandakaki

Carmona retusa
Tsaang-gubat

Strelitzia reginae
Bird of paradise

Podocarpus macrophyllus
Maki

General Planting Concept

Agro-resilient Technology Zone

The selected plant species on the zone is dominated by commercial crops given its focus on agricultural production.

trees

Mangifera indica
Mango

Cocos nuciferas
Coconut

Citrus maxima
Pomelo

Polyscias nodosa
Malapapaya

Pterocarpus indicus
Narra

shrubs

Ixora chinensis
Santan

Tabernaemontana pandacaqui
Pandakaki

Carmona retusa
Tsaang-gubat

Strelitzia reginae
Bird of paradise

Podocarpus macrophyllus
Maki

crops

Ipomoea batatas
Sweet potato

Momordica charantia
Ampalaya

Solanum melongana
Eggplant

Solanum lycopersicum
Tomato

Cucurbita maxima
Kalabasa

Masterplan Budgetary Estimates

This is a ballpark figure of the overall costs of the proposed plan. Note that the figure can still increase once a detailed estimation is performed.

The zones were divided into two classes: highly and moderately modified. The highly modified zones were priced at 500 pesos per square meter. This included the multifunctional agriculture, flood-resilient agriculture, agroforestry, agro-industrial, multifunctional fisheries, and agro-resilient technology zones. On the one hand, moderately modified zones included the riparian restoration and forest zones. The price per square meter was set at 100 pesos given that the majority of the interventions in this class rely on nature-based strategies whereas the former employed numerous structural interventions. The estimated cost of transforming Ilagan into a flood-adaptive agricultural city was priced at 265 billion pesos.

Zone	Area (sqm)	Cost (per square meter)	Total
<i>Riparian Restoration</i>	22,153,227.16	100	2,215,322,715.60
<i>Multifunctional Agriculture</i>	55,753,903.4	500	27,876,951,701.50
<i>Flood-resilient Agriculture</i>	142,770,308.6	500	71,385,154,305.00
<i>Agroforestry</i>	92,840,199.91	500	46,420,099,953.00
<i>Forest</i>	93,052,607.44	100	9,305,260,744.40
<i>Agro-industrial</i>	20,932,086	500	10,466,043,000.00
<i>Multifunctional Fisheries</i>	33,620,888.31	500	16,810,444,157.00
<i>Agro-resilient Technology</i>	162,360,161.5	500	81,180,080,767.00
<i>Total</i>	623,483,382.4		265,659,357,343.50

Year-long Scenario

This section showcases the dynamics of the proposed agricultural flood adaptative landscape. It provides information on the agricultural activities appropriate for each month.

How to read the maps?

The cropping calendar adheres to two cropping seasons: dry and wet. It must be noted that the maps are sequenced privileging the viewpoint of a flood-adaptive calendar. The dry season marks the start of the cropping calendar. Hence, the maps begin in December--the proposed start of the dry season for affected farms.

Additionally, the agricultural activities are categorized into flood-affected and non-affected farms. Icons and labels directly placed on the symbology of the two categories are extended to farms that do not share the same boundaries where the elements are placed. Focus on the line pattern of the farm category instead of the colorful background indicating the location of each zone.

december

flooding season + dry season

january

dry season

february

dry season

march

dry season

april

dry season

may

wet season

june

wet season

july

wet season

august

wet season

processing produce

- flooded agricultural lands
- non-flooded agricultural lands

september

wet season

processing produce

- flooded agricultural lands
- non-flooded agricultural lands

october

flooding season

processing produce

alternative livelihoods

- flooded agricultural lands
- non-flooded agricultural lands

november

flooding season

processing produce

alternative livelihoods

- flooded agricultural lands
- non-flooded agricultural lands

august

wet season

september

wet season

october

flooding season

november

flooding season

Let's take a review!

What you will do:

Synthesize your learning

Turn the synthesis into a flood-adaptive strategy

Priorities for action

For the LGU

What are the main issues the LGU has to deal with to address the impact of agricultural flooding in Ilagan?

How do you think the masterplan contribute to agricultural flood adaptation in the city?

What proposed policies must be prioritized to successfully implement the masterplan?

Priorities for action

For the farmers

What current farming practices worsen the effects of flooding in your farmlands?

Empty rounded rectangular box for response.

What agricultural adjustments do you need to make as part of agricultural flood adaptation?

Empty rounded rectangular box for response.

What zone does your farm fall into? What specific solutions are recommended for you farm class?

Empty rounded rectangular box for response.

Agrikultura ta Paddakal na Danum

A Synthesis of Collective Knowledge through a Farmer-Nature Landscape Approach for the Agricity of Ilagan, Isabela

end.

